

Ten myths about open science

Open science, a movement for research transparency and access to scientific information, is shrouded in a number of myths, often stemming from the lack of understanding of its basic principles. What is the truth about open science?

You can only publish open access through paid open journals.

You can use the so-called green open access, i.e., publish your article in a traditional, subscription-based journal that allows you to store a version of your article in a publicly accessible repository under a license agreement. Some publishers, such as the Karolinum Press, even offer to publish an article free of charge (the so-called platinum or diamond open access).

Open access does not protect copyright.

Copyright protection is applied in the same way for both the traditional and the open access publishing models. The options for disposition of the work, including various ways of use of the work are then specifically determined by licenses (e.g., Creative Commons license).

Open access is responsible for predatory journals.

Journals of low quality have always been here, however, with the growth of the Internet and online communication, predatory journals have abused the paid open access model of publishing to gain profit. It is therefore important to choose the journal for your article with great care.

I don't have any data.

Research data can be characterised as any information that has been collected, observed, generated, or created to validate or reproduce your research findings. Depending on the type of research you are doing, research data can take various forms such as spreadsheets, text files, audio / video recordings, questionnaire forms, lab protocols, computer code, etc.

My data are not useful to anyone else, there is no point sharing them.

Your data can be used not only by colleagues in your field but also by researchers from other disciplines, who may apply different methods of analysis or combine them with other research data which could lead to new findings. Apart from researchers, your data may also be useful to educators, policy makers or general public.

Authors must pay publication fees from their own pocket.

If you choose to publish in an open or hybrid journal which requires the payment of a publication fee (gold open access), it is possible to use discounts or waivers of the publication fee with the publishers that have an agreement with Charles University. Publication fees are also an eligible cost for projects of most grant agencies.

Open journals have a low, if not no impact factor.

Open access can have a positive effect on the growth of citation rate. Publishing open access does not mean avoiding standard publishing and peer review procedures or any decrease in output quality.

Data management plan (DMP) is just another useless administrative formality.

A data management plan makes it easier for researchers to navigate their data, helps them anticipate potential problems and ensures that the data are complete, accurate and reliable. A DMP also helps to ensure continuity and consistency, especially in long-term projects, and it can help with data sharing.

Open science is just a hype that will go away.

An increasing number of research funders include open science requirements in their policies, many journals are adopting open data policies requiring that authors share underlying data for their papers, and open science practices are also getting a solid ground in national and international policies. It is a trend, that is going to stay.

Open science is only relevant for the STEM disciplines.

Open science aims to encompass scientific communication as a whole, including Social Sciences and Humanities. Sometimes the terms open scholarship, open research, or open knowledge are being used instead of open science.